

Elongation ability in deepwater rices

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We studied the elongation ability of 12 deepwater rice varieties and 24 advanced breeding lines during 1989 wet season. Entries seeded in pots were submerged in 120-cm-deep water 42-49 d after seeding.

Internode, leaf sheath, and leaf blade lengths were measured on 10 plants before and after flooding. Recovery or submergence tolerance was scored 10 d after water was drained.

By and large, the traditional floating rices had higher total elongation than did the breeding lines (see table). Total plant elongation after 7 d water treatment ranged from 8.5 cm (entry ACC33745 was rejected and is not in the table) to 66.5 cm (TCA4).

TCA4 had the highest internode

Plant elongation and regeneration ability of rices with different deepwater survival strategies.^a

Variety	Elongation (cm)			Submergence tolerance score
	Internode	Leaf sheath	Leaf blade	
TCA4	<u>51.5</u>	7.6	7.4	7
NDGR401	<u>49.0</u>	2.7	3.7	5
NDGR406	<u>42.7</u>	8.0	5.0	5
NDGR404	<u>42.3</u>	3.7	<u>16.4</u>	5
ACC38876	<u>34.3</u>	9.4	7.3	5
Jalmagna	<u>31.3</u>	5.0	6.0	9
NDGR402	<u>28.4</u>	6.3	<u>18.6</u>	3
920356	22.0	4.7	<u>20.3</u>	3
IR11141-6-1-4	16.9	8.4	<u>18.7</u>	5
Nam Sagui 19	13.1	9.6	2.7	3
IR39657-4-502-1-3-2	12.0	4.7	12.0	5
TCA7819	11.0	<u>20.3</u>	10.0	5
IR39657-B-B-1	4.0	<u>15.7</u>	4.0	5
ACC18973	2.0	<u>16.0</u>	5.0	3
FR 13A	0.4	<u>20.6</u>	4.0	3

^aUnderlining indicates relatively high reliance of the plant on the corresponding survival strategy.

elongation, followed by NDGR404 and NDGR406.

Leaf sheath and leaf blade elongation as high as 15.7-20.6 cm were recorded in 920356, ACC18973, TCA7819, NDGR402, IR39657-B-B-1, and FR13A. Since leaf elongation ability is limited, these entries might be suitable for areas that have sudden floods of limited depth.

Varieties with submergence tolerance scores 1-3 will be helpful in areas prone to

sudden submergence.

Higher elongation values indicate relatively high reliance on the corresponding survival strategy. Some varieties rely on internode elongation, leaf (sheath, blade) elongation, and/or submergence tolerance. Breeding strategies could incorporate some or all of these survival characters, depending on the target area. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Utilization of sources of resistance to bacterial blight (BE) in China

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We screened 99 rice cultivars and lines against BB caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo) at CNRRI Experiment Station during Apr-Oct 1990.

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in two rows of 14 hills each at 20- × 20-cm spacing, with two replications. One row each of local susceptible check Jin-Gang 30 and resistant check IR26 were transplanted between each entry and around the experimental field.

The plot was fertilized with 75-37.5-25 kg NPK/ha.

Seven pathogenic groups of Xoo with varying virulence, based on their reaction on five Chinese differentials, were provided by Yin Shangzhi, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences (Table 1).

Test plants were clip-inoculated with a concentration of 3×10^8 CFU/ml from maximum tillering to initial booting stage.

Disease incidence was scored 21 d after inoculation.

Eight varieties showed resistance to the pathogenic groups (Table 2). They have good agronomic traits and high yield potential, and have been used as resistance sources for breeding.

Given the geographical distribution of the BB pathogenic groups and the rice varietal types appropriate for different rice cropping regions, *Xa-3* resistance sources are best in japonica rice cropping

Table 1. Pathogenic groups of Xoo in China.

Pathogenic group	Representative isolate	Reaction ^a on indicated differential varieties				
		Jin-Gang 30	Tetep	Nan-Jing 15	Java 14	IR26
I	JS97-2	S	R	R	R	R
II	KS-1-21	S	S	R	R	R
III	JS158-2	S	S	S	R	R
IV	Zhejiang 173	S	S	S	S	R
V	1358	S	S	R	R	S
VI	OS-198	S	R	S	R	R
VII	JS49-6	S	R	S	S	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Resistance of rice cultivars (lines) to 7 pathogenic groups of BB in China 21 d after inoculation.

Variety (line)	Reaction ^a to pathogenic group							Origin	Use
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII		
Milyang 23	1	5	3	5	3	5	5	Korea	Hybridization
DV85	5	7	3	3	1	5	3	Bangladesh	Hybridization
IR54	3	3	3	3	5	3	3	IRRI	Hybridization
IRBB 7	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	IRRI	Resistance source
BR568-15-4-2-2-3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	Bangladesh	Resistance source
C702015	1	3	3	3	3	3	5	Taiwan (China)	Resistance source
C722355	1	3	3	5	5	3	3	Taiwan (China)	Resistance source
Suwon	3391333351							Korea	Resistance source

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale 0-9.

regions of the northern part beyond the Yangtze River. *Xa-3*, *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, *Xa-6*, or *Xa-7* resistance sources are best in indica-japonica rice cropping regions along the

Yangtze River. *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, and *Xa-7* resistance sources are needed in indica rice cropping regions in the south China coastal area. □

Resistance to tungro in some wild relatives of rice

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We tested 16 accessions of wild rice *Oryza* spp. for antibiosis to green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Distant, resistance to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) infection, and tolerance for tungro.

To test for antibiosis, a 10-d-old seedling of each accession was placed in a test tube with five GLH nymphs (2d instar), with 10 replications. Antibiosis of each accession was rated on a 1-5 scale by counting surviving GLH nymphs every day for 3 d. Those same seedlings (15-d-old) were inoculated with 10 viruliferous GLH adults/seedling for 4 h. Leaves were individually sampled 3 wk after inoculation, and tested for RTBV and RTSV by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. Disease severity of each accession was scored at 4 wk after

Reactions of wild species of rice to GLH and tungro disease.

Genome	Species	IRGC acc. no.	Origin	Anti-biosis to GLH ^a	Plants tested (no.)	Infected plants ^b (%)			Average severity ^c
						B+S	B	S	
AA	<i>O. nivara</i>	102463	Bangladesh	5	38	74	26	0	3
		102175	India	1	18	0	78	0	5
		105333	India	1	49	2	59	0	2
		105409	Sri Lanka	5	39	69	18	3	2
		105417	Sri Lanka	4	18	50	11	6	2
BB	<i>O. punctata</i>	105456	Sri Lanka	4	3	67	33	0	5
		103896	Tanzania	1	17	0	53	0	2
BBCC	<i>O. minuta</i>	105158	Kenya	2	49	0	37	0	3
		101126	Philippines	1	20	5	50	0	3
CC	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	101141	Philippines	1	36	0	56	0	5
		105414	Sri Lanka	2	47	47	43	0	5
CC	<i>O. officinalis</i>	105365	Thailand	1	27	0	0	0	2
		105394	China	3	32	9	81	0	3/7 ^d
		105660	Sri Lanka	1	13	15	31	8	5
CC	<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	105448	Sri Lanka		4	50	25	0	3
		100914	Mexico	1	23	57	0	13	3
CCDD	<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	Mexico	1	23	57	0	13	3
AA	<i>O. sativa</i> (check varieties)	ARC11554	India	1	54	2	39	0	3
		Utri Merah	Indonesia	5	54	2	52	0	3
		TN1	Taiwan	5	53	96	4	0	9
		IR22	Philippines	5	57	90	10	0	9

^aScale of 1 (resistant) to 5 (susceptible). ^bInfected with both RTBV and RTSV (B+S), with RTSV (S), or with RTBV (B). ^cScale 1 (no symptoms) to 9 (more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration), using Nasanuddin et al scale.

^dSegregating.

inoculation.

One accession of *O. officinalis* (105365) showed high antibiosis to GLH and resistance to both RTBV and RTSV infection (see table). Two accessions of *O. nivara* (102175, 105333), two of *O. punctata* (103896, 105158), and two of *O. minuta* (101126, 101141) showed high antibiosis to GLH and resistance to RTSV infection. Even with low antibiosis to GLH and severe infection with RTBV and RTSV, three accessions of *O. nivara* (102463, 105409, 105417) showed low scores for symptom severity, indicating tolerance for tungro.

These results suggest that a number of new sources of resistance to both RTBV and RTSV may be found among the wild rices. □

Distribution of rice varieties resistant to bacterial blight (BB) in Yunnan, China

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We screened 4,091 Yunnan rice varieties for resistance to BB caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* strain Jiangling 691: 6% were resistant, 84% were susceptible, and 10% were moderately resistant. The frequency of resistance differed within rice classifications (Table 1).

Resistance was more frequent among glutinous rices.

Table 2 shows more resistant varieties among japonica-irrigated-glutinous, japonica-irrigated-nonglutinous, and japonica-upland-glutinous rices. Mean

Table 1. Distribution of BB-resistant rices in Yunnan, China.

Classification	Varieties tested (no.)	Resistant varieties	
		no.	%
Indica	2186	83	3.8
Japonica	1905	159	8.4
Irrigated	3233	202	6.2
Upland	858	40	4.7
Nonglutinous	3183	159	5.0
Glutinous	908	83	9.1